

3. Methodology

3.1 Data Acquisition and Pre-processing

This study utilized three autism spectrum disorder screening datasets provided by Fadi Thabtah from the UC Irvine Machine Learning Repository, stratified by age group: children, adolescents, and adults. Each dataset contains an equal number of samples and identical variables, including demographic characteristics (age, gender, ethnicity, country of residence) and individual item scores from the AQ-10 screening questionnaire. Table 1 summarizes all variables by age subgroup. The specific screening instrument administered varied according to the participant's age group.

Prior to analysis, the data underwent preprocessing to ensure quality and completeness. Records containing missing values (NaN) were identified and removed from the dataset to maintain data integrity and prevent biased parameter estimates that can result from incomplete observations. Given the relatively small proportion of missing data, listwise deletion was employed. All subsequent analyses were performed on complete cases, eliminating potential biases introduced by missing data imputation methods.

3.2 Data Analysis and Validation

All analyses were conducted in Python using the following libraries: NumPy for numerical operations, Pandas for data manipulation, XGBoost for model implementation, scikit-learn for data preprocessing and evaluation metrics, and Matplotlib for visualization. We employed an XGBoost classifier for each age-stratified dataset. XGBoost, a gradient boosting algorithm, was selected for its robust classification performance and ability to capture complex, nonlinear relationships between predictor variables and diagnostic outcomes. Each age group was analyzed independently to preserve developmental differences in ASD presentation.

Within each dataset, an 80-10-10 split was used to partition data into training, validation, and testing subsets. The training set was used to fit the XGBoost model, while the validation set enabled hyperparameter tuning and model selection to prevent overfitting. Key hyperparameters optimized included maximum tree depth, learning rate, and subsample ratio, which were tuned to balance model complexity and generalization performance.

The testing set, held out from all training procedures, provided an unbiased evaluation of final model performance. Models were assessed using accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, F1-score, and area under the ROC curve (AUC-ROC). Additionally, we utilized SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values to quantify feature importance and interpret the model's predictions. SHAP analysis was conducted separately for male and female subgroups within each age category to examine potential sex-based differences in the variables contributing most significantly to diagnostic outcomes. This approach allowed us to identify which demographic characteristics and AQ-10 questionnaire items were most influential in predicting autism spectrum disorder diagnosis and to determine whether these predictive patterns differed between males and females.